

OPEN EDUCATIONAL PRACTICES FOR RESEARCH EFFECTIVENESS TO RESEARCH SCHOLAR

**K. Sathish Kumar^{1*}, M. Mahendra Prabu¹, G. Kalaiyarasan¹, R. Ramnath¹,
N. Sasi Kumar¹, Mani Mookkiah¹, M. Arul Kumar^{1, 2}, Rahul B^{1, 3}**

¹Department of Education, Alagappa University, Karaikudi -630 003, India.

²Department of International Business, Alagappa University, Karaikudi -630 003, India.

³Department of Computer Science, Alagappa University, Karaikudi -630 003, India.

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6036-7395>

ABSTRACT

The current study conducted to determine the degree of efficacy of research scholars, and a significant difference was found concerning type in universities and experience. The sample included 525 research scholars researching state universities of Tamil Nadu. The tool used for the present study was the research scholar's effectiveness Scale (RES). It was discovered that there is a modest degree of research scholar effectiveness among university-level research scholars. There is a significant difference found among the research scholars in their research effectiveness concerning the type of universities, and a significant difference is not found concerning the experience. It advised that research scholar's effectiveness can be enhanced through various open educational resources, which can be made known to the university research scholars.

Keywords: Research Scholars Effectiveness, Open Educational Resources, Open Educational Practices, experience,

I. INTRODUCTION

Open Educational Resources (OER) are teaching and learning materials that are freely available online for everyone to use[1],[2]. Open educational resources vary from open learning in that they are largely curriculum-focused, while open learning provides both content and instructional facilities, such as specially crafted online courses, built-in learner support, and evaluation [3],[4]. Open educational services are available in a variety of multimedia formats [5], includes online textbooks, video recorded lectures, YouTube clips, web-based textual resources tailored for self-study, animations, and simulations [6], Any MOOCs, graphical diagrams and graphics, or even evaluation materials such as assessments with programmed answers [7],[8]. OER may also contain PowerPoint presentations or lecture notes in pdf format. However, in order to be considered open educational materials, they must be publicly accessible for at least educational use.

Research scholar effectiveness means the optimum level of efficiency and productivity on the part of scholars. It refers to the height of learning and maturity in the life span of a researcher. Presently researchers are supposed to maintain the high and relevant standards for academic success besides maintaining student centered, achievement oriented classroom environments [9]. A mixture of subject matter, experience, and an appreciation of the essence of effective teaching itself will provide a firm basis for effectiveness. In today's world, a teacher's job entails a variety of responsibilities in addition to teaching and studying. These include imbibing new information and skills keeping abreast of technological innovations and dealing with research scholars, professors, and community [10]. The current study was conducted to determine the efficacy of research scholars so that they can be educated by OER to improve their teaching performance [28].

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Author & Year	Aim/Objective	Methodology		Result/ Findings & Future Research
		Sample Size/ Respondent	Design/Tools	
Blum-Smith et al., 2021	This paper discusses how a collection of Facilitating learner-centered interactions	The team was chosen from four MOOCs with specifically specified learner-	How do facilitator teams explain putting their learner-centered pedagogical goals into action using MOOC platforms? We used observational, in-depth	This study adds to the ongoing work of articulating the content and precision of teaching in learner-centered pedagogy, as well as the

	in MOOCs can be used.	centered goals. The educators on these teams designed and facilitated the classes in which they were participating.	questioning techniques. We used deliberate sampling. They arranged semi-structured interviews with both of the teams.	ongoing difficulties of enacting the pedagogy in huge, multimedia spaces. We addressed six facilitator acts in the findings—"giving up power," "distributing facilitation," "being live," "amplifying," "modelling," and "being explicit"—that answered the research question of how facilitation teams represented enacting their learner-centered pedagogical aspirations via MOOC platforms [11].
J. Wang et al., 2021	The current study aims to increase understanding of the factors that influence DER (Digital Educational Resources)-sharing behaviour among rural school teachers.	A total of 709 rural teachers were included in the report. Participants included primary and secondary school teachers from rural parts in southwest China.	With an online survey, a sampling method is used to collect data. Exploratory factor analyses (EFA) were performed using IBM SPSS 25 and dispositional variables, and confirmatory factor analyses (CFA) were performed using Mplus 8.3. Cronbach's alpha is included.	Internal and external inspiration were found to have a substantial impact on emotions, as well as exchanging behaviour inside and outside of education, in the research. Internal motivation, on the other hand, affected both attitude and communication actions positively, while external motivation influenced both negatively. Teachers' networking behaviour on various online sharing platforms can be the subject of future study[12].
Nipa&Kerma nshachi, 2020	The aim of this paper is to examine the value of OER materials for engineering students as well as students with majors in other (non-engineering) fields.	The samples were gathered from both students and businesses.	The first class used a web-based digital OER scheme, while the second class used a conventional textbook. A survey was produced and circulated to determine 19 different facets of students' lives.	The results of this study will help universities and colleges devote financial capital more efficiently to the production and delivery of OER materials [13].
Dai et al., 2020	The aim of this research is to look into the factors that influence the desire to learn in a Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) environment.	We had 17 briefings with roughly 835 students from three Chinese universities.	On a 7-point Likert scale, all of the item questions were formatted.	The results of these significant determinants, as well as their internal hierarchical relationships, will provide Chinese educators with analytical insights and scientific data to help them design successful learning assistance or intervention to inspire learners to continue learning[14].
Santiago & Ray, 2020	The aim of this paper is to explain services in institutional libraries that promote the publication of open educational tools (OER). Insights, prospects, and challenges related to the wider open education movement are discussed.	The University of Houston and the University of Washington are two examples of case studies.	This paper presents two case studies discussing the growth of OER publishing systems at large, public research universities. Each initiative takes an Author DIY approach to publishing support and is still in the early stages of promoting OER acceptance and development.	They highlight obstacles and opportunities for librarians who promote OER projects, such as integrating current OER publication models, managing institutional culture, pushing OER services beyond availability, and sustaining and scaling OER programmes with changing institutional support[15].
Luo et al., 2020	The aim of this study is to look at OER adoption techniques that facilitate efficient and successful design	The research was based on 51 OER studies conducted in countries	On a global scope, this comprehensive literature review investigated the scientific trends present in current studies.	The findings of this study show that (1) discoverability, sustainability, and remixing are major obstacles to OER undermining conventional

	while also growing stakeholder and institutional support for OER initiatives.	spanning five continents.		textbook models, and (2) there is no significant change in learning outcomes when teachers use OER; and (3) OER as teaching methods can be difficult to execute, but when correctly crafted, they can be effective in supporting meaningful learning outcomes [16].
Littenberg-Tobias & Reich, 2020	Can vast open online courses (MOOCs) become a global on-ramp for the access to new areas for underrepresented communities as they turn toward technical degree and diploma programmes?	At least one of the supply chain management MOOCs has been completed by 81,000 students.	Design of a mixed-methods analysis. We used a grounded theory approach to contextual coding of the data. Within the framework of this programme, we tried to categorise and test these conclusions, which we refer to as design theories, regarding MicroMasters and MOOC-based integrated master's degree programmes.	Male students and students with master's degrees were more likely to complete the online curriculum, according to our findings. Students in the hybrid graduate programme received higher average scores in their in-person classes than students in the residential programme. This study's results demonstrate how emerging online learning technologies can fill narrow niches while struggling to fix wider equity concerns [17].
Zhang et al., 2020	This research provides a systematic analysis focused on published articles on open educational resources (OER) and open educational practises (OEP) for learning mobility, with a focus on disabled students.	The samples were gathered 31 systematic review papers.	This research offers a systematic overview focusing on peer-reviewed papers.	For disabled students, the amount of available open software programmes was smaller than the number of non-open software programmes. Nine countries have led studies on online educational infrastructure (OER) and open educational activities (OEP) for more transparent learning. Ecuador had 11 articles, Spain had six, the United Kingdom had four, Greece had three, Ireland had two, Turkey, Uruguay, Tunisia, and Italy had one[18].
Todorinova & Wilkinson, 2020	Faculty opinions on the award scheme, their encounters with OER, and their participation in open textbook authoring were all gathered in the survey.	This survey looked at the views of 56 Rutgers University professors who won OAT awards as part of a textbook affordability campaign.	The course materials used in revised OAT courses, the financial opportunity reward presented, and the effect of the new course materials on students were all explicitly addressed in survey questions. It's just about demographics.	According to the responses, the curriculum is well received, and funds are sufficient for the adoption of new course materials. They also show that even among participating faculty, their understanding and use of OER, as well as their participation in writing open textbooks, varies greatly [19].
Schellinger & Coghill, 2020	This essay would look at how open education services (OERs) can be used to help reduce the cost of medical and nursing school.	The essay was written as an analysis focused on previously published articles.	Analysis based on articles that have been written.	Initiatives have to begin somewhere. Librarians should be shift managers. Shift may also be facilitated by top-level officials such as chancellors, presidents, provosts, vice chancellors, and deans. Librarians should strive into alliances outside of their institutions and add OER to their respective institutions [20].
Maina et al., 2020	The aim of this project is to build, measure, and certify students' DC in European	Teachers from multiple European Union nations, two	Via three stages of growth, the study used a design-based analysis approach: A focus group with teachers and interviews with learning designers were used to gather	Participants took part in a role-playing exercise in which they played the roles of teacher and pupil. The step

	primary and secondary schools using a methodological and technical approach.	learning planners, and four researchers took part in the participatory design process.	Phase 1 results, which focused on the design process and design outcomes (CAS). The data for Step 2 came from a teacher survey on integrating and incorporating CAS on a dedicated site. Finally, phase 3 data was collected from a survey of MOOC users and a final survey of teachers who took part in the pilots.	presented additional insight on teacher practise in the fields of instruction and evaluation [21].
Lee, 2020	Who, where, and for what purpose does online distance education become available?	In August of this year, the above search yielded 137 returns. As a result, 29 articles were chosen for printing.	The following search criteria were used to find papers based on their title, abstract, and keywords: "free education" "university" "higher education" "online education" "online learning" "distance education" "distance learning." I used a grounded theory approach to evaluate the papers that were picked.	Despite the growing urgency of the social mission to render Education for Everyone among diverse actors, the findings indicate that a strong picture of the actual mechanism of OEP in real-life higher education environments, as well as clarification about how such actors currently represent vulnerable learners, is missing[22].
Kumar & Kumar, 2020	The aim of this research was to look at the variables that impact learner satisfaction in the classroom.	There were 23 scale items and five multiple choice questions on the questionnaire. A total of 300 responses were received from different states in India, with 223 of them remaining accurate.	The standardised questionnaire has been modified for this analysis. (i) Course Content - CC (6 items) (ii) CD-ROM Course Distribution (4 items) (iii) Course Assessment - CA (4 items) (iv) Course Assistance - CS (3 items). Age, ethnicity, and occupation demographic data were gathered.	Swayam and Coursera were the most popular MOOC portals, with 145 respondents (65%) each, followed by Edx (15%), Udacity (10%), and FutureLearn (5%). (5 percent). There were 109 men (49%) and 114 women in the poll (51 percent). The current research looked at how satisfied participants were with MOOCs offered by Swayam, Coursera, FutureLearn, and Edx [23].
Gupta & Pathania, 2020	The aim of this analysis was to evaluate the effect of the Google Classroom Portal on teacher education.	A total of 60 students, both males and females, were drawn from a single college of education in Jammu region. The M.Ed. class has 45 students and the M.A. Education programme has 15.	In this study, the Google Classroom Evaluation Survey was used. The students were chosen using a purposeful sampling methodology.	Students could use online services on a daily basis. Students felt satisfied and accomplished, and they were comfortable collaborating collaboratively with other students. Students were also delighted to be able to print lessons and exercise materials from tools that their teachers had uploaded [24].
Pitt et al., 2020	Using open textbooks to help open teaching activities.	Educators in the United Kingdom were surveyed. During September 2018, over 4000 UK educators were invited to participate by email.	The survey had 25 questions and was split into two parts. The demographic questions were the subject of the first part of the study. The survey's second half focused on textbook use and logic.	Which focused on open educational resource awareness, textbook usage and justification, open textbook awareness and use, and open licencing? The results suggest that open textbook adoption is on the rise, with the ability to promote a wide variety of open educational activities. The results point to techniques for fostering pedagogical creativity and student access through universal implementation of open educational services [25].
George & Casey, 2020	Increased Open Educational	case study; Embry-Riddle	This is a case study of a university with a large online and distributed network that	As a result, an internal suggestion was made about

	Resources for Curriculum Development and Delivery by Collaboration Between the Library, Faculty, and Instructional Design.	Aeronautical University	helps professors to monitor course planning, timelines, and curriculum.	how to structure communication with the Library and course creators, as well as how to view the chosen OERs in the Learning Management System. The results looked at how using OERs in the classroom redesigned course assignments and tests, as well as promoting the development of original OERs in discipline-specific topics and content [26].
Y. Wang et al., 2020	Linked to the inability to keep the learning process going, which results in poor completion rates.	An online questionnaire (N= 638) was filled out by participants in Anhui Agricultural University's MOOCs to collect data.	The research model was put to the test using structural equations. SEM is a tool for defining, estimating, and analysing causal link- ship models.	The findings show that perceived utility, learning behaviours, subjective standards, perceived behavioural influence, and learning behaviour all have a major impact on learning success, but perceived ease of use does not [27].

According to this related literature review, the investigators find the current research gap is open educational practices. A particularly open educational practice for research scholars is a minimum number of articles only available [29], [30]. Then the researcher chooses the current research gap as “open educational practices for research scholar effectiveness in the state universities of Tamilnadu.”

III. OBJECTIVES

- To find out the level of research Effectiveness of scholars at universities level.
- To find out if there is any significant difference in research effectiveness found between rural and urban background research scholars at universities level.
- To find out if there is any significant difference in research effectiveness between teachers whose experience is below 3 years and above 3 years at universities level.

IV. HYPOTHESIS

- The level of researcher effectiveness of research scholars at universities level is found to be moderate.
- There is no significant difference in research effectiveness found between rural and urban background research scholars at universities level.
- There is no significant difference in research effectiveness between research scholars whose experience is below 3 years and above 3 years at universities level.

V. METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in state universities of Tamilnadu research scholars. This survey method was adopted to collect the data from the simple random sampling method. All the research scholars are doing research in the state universities of Tamilnadu constituted the population of the present study [31],[32]. The sample was selected on random basis from the population and the total sample comprises of 525 research scholars doing research at universities level [39],[40]. Research effectiveness Scale (RES) was consists of fifty items under five dimensions such as preparation of Teaching and Planning [41], Classroom Management [42], Knowledge of Subject- Matter [43], research scholars Characteristics [44] and Interpersonal Relations[45]. The test – retest reliability of the scale was found to be 0.63. In the present study, the investigator analyzed the data by using appropriate statistical techniques [33],[34].

VI. ANALYSIS, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hypothesis 1: The level of research effectiveness of state universities of Tamilnadu research scholars is found to be moderate.

Table-1: levels of teacher effectiveness

Research Effectiveness	Variable	N	Mean	SD	t' value	Remark
	Rural Background	150	161.74	7.05	2.72	Significant
	Urban Background	160	163.98	7.48		

It is observed from the above table all the research scholars are having moderate level of research effectiveness. Researcher effectiveness will make them perform better in the classroom which will directly benefit to the quality education and better relationship with students. So, it is necessary to develop the research effectiveness with an appropriate intervention strategy[35],[38].

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in research effectiveness found between rural and urban background researchers at universities level.

Table 2 Significant difference in research effectiveness found between rural and urban background research scholars at universities level

Research Effectiveness		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Level	Low Level	0	0	0	0
	Moderate Level	525	100.0	100.0	100.0
	High Level	0	0	0	0

It is inferred that the rural and urban background research scholar differ significantly in research effectiveness, further, the research effectiveness of rural background researchers is better than the urban background researchers. It may be due to direct supervision and monitoring system available in urban background which is more effective than the rural background researchers[36],[37].

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in research effectiveness between research scholars whose experience is below 3 years and above 3 years at universities level.

Table 3: Significant difference in research effectiveness between research scholars whose experience is below 3 years and above 3 years at universities level

Variable	Experience	N	Mean	SD	t' value	Remark
Research Effectiveness	Below 3 years	508	162.98	7.56	0.70	Not Significant
	Above 3 years	17	163.70	8.27		

It is evident from the above table that the calculated critical ratio value is found to be 0.70 for research effectiveness and is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that the research scholars whose experience below 3 years and above 3 years do not differ significantly in research effectiveness. Further the mean value of research scholars whose experience below 3years and above 3 years more or less same. We may infer that years of experience has no impact on the research effectiveness. So, in future, the researchers and policy makers need not to give much importance to years of experience on research effectiveness[37],[38].

VII. CONCLUSION AND RECOMENTATIONS

The present investigation was done to find out the level of research effectiveness and the influence of state universities and experience on research effectiveness. It was found out that there exists moderate level of research effectiveness found among research scholars at state universities of Tamilnadu level. There is significant difference found among the research scholars in their research effectiveness with respect to state universities and significant difference is not found with respect to experience. The level of research effectiveness can be enhancing through various open educational resources. If the research scholars are made

aware of these resources, they will be updated and improve their efficiency. The moderate level of research effectiveness can be enhanced through various refreshing programmes and research scholars can be encouraged to equip themselves and updated by using various online educational resources. Rural background researchers have low level of research effectiveness. This is because of their lack of accountability to the society. They are subjected to frequent transfers and it becomes impossible for them to completely understand their researchers before they teach. Hence, such researchers must be allowed to research in the same universities, for at least three to five years.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to thank my HOD Dr. G. Kalaiyaran for his directions, as well as acknowledging the support of Dr R. Ramnath, Dr N. Sasi Kumar for encouraging to developing the content of this paper. Special Thanks to Arul, Rajkumar, Prathab and Gobi for their unexpected help and support.

VIII. REFERENCES

- [1] M. Mahendraprabu, K. Sathish Kumar, M. Mani, P. Saravana Kumar , "Open Educational Resources And Their Educational Practices In Higher Education," Mukta Shabd Journal, Vol. 10, No. 2, Pp. 527-540, Feb. 2021, Doi: 10.0014.Msj.2021.V10i2.0086781.118753.
- [2] N Mahalakshmi, M Mahendraprabu, Mani Mookkiah, Sathish Kumar, "Work Values Of Secondary Grade Teachers Based On Certain Selected Variables," Journal Of Xi'an University Of Architecture & Technology., Vol. 12, No. 3, Pp. 4910-4918, 2020.
- [3] Mani Mookkiah, Mahendraprabu, Kalaiyaran, Ramnath, Sasikumar, Sathish Kumar, Sathiyaraj , "Yoga Based Intervention Strategies In Accelerating Self-Efficacy Among Primary School Teachers," Elementary Education Online, Vol. 20, No. 4. Pp. 794-805, 2021, Doi: 10.17051/llkonline.2021.04.85.
- [4] Kumar, K., Mahendraprabu, M. Open Educational Practices Of Swayam Programme Among Research Scholars. Educ Inf Technol (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10639-021-10495-2>
- [5] Mookkiah, M., & Prabu, M. M, Impact Of Social Media On The Academic Achievement Of Secondary School Students, Journal Of Xi'an University Of Architecture & Technology, 12(3), 3106-3109 (2020).
- [6] Prabu, M. M. Redesigning And Restructuring Teacher Education Programme, An International Refereed, Peer Reviewed And Indexed Quarterly Journal In Arts, Commerce, Education & Social Sciences, 5(2), 28-30 (2016).
- [7] Prabu, M. M. Curriculum Transaction For Quality Teacher Education, An International Indexed, Refereed & Peer Reviewed Bi-Annual Journal In Education, 3(2) 133-134 (2016).
- [8] M. Mahendra Prabu, Collaborative And Cooperative Learning In Choice Based Credit System, Research Dimensions, 3(2), 1-5 (2016).
- [9] M. Mahendraprabu, G. Arumugam, A Study Of Environmental Awareness Ability Of Higher Secondary Students, International Journal Of Modern Research And Reviews, 2(11), 508-510 (2014).
- [10] M. Mahendraprabu, G. Arumugam, Knowledge Of Higher Secondary Students About Communicable Diseases And Their Mental Health, Conflux Journal Of Education, 2(3), 76-79 (2014).
- [11] S. Blum-Smith, M. M. Yurkofsky, And K. Brennan, "Stepping Back And Stepping In: Facilitating Learner-Centered Experiences In Moocs," Comput. Educ., Vol. 160, Jan. 2021, Doi: 10.1016/J.Compedu.2020.104042.
- [12] J. Wang, D. E. H. Tigelaar, And W. Admiraal, "Rural Teachers' Sharing Of Digital Educational Resources: From Motivation To Behavior," Comput. Educ., Vol. 161, Feb. 2021, Doi: 10.1016/J.Compedu.2020.104055.
- [13] T. J. Nipa And S. Kermanshachi, "Assessment Of Open Educational Resources (Oer) Developed In Interactive Learning Environments," Educ. Inf. Technol., Vol. 25, No. 4, Pp. 2521-2547, Jul. 2020, Doi: 10.1007/S10639-019-10081-7.
- [14] H. M. Dai, T. Teo, N. A. Rappa, And F. Huang, "Explaining Chinese University Students' Continuance Learning Intention In The Mooc Setting: A Modified Expectation Confirmation Model Perspective," Comput. Educ., Vol. 150, Jun. 2020, Doi: 10.1016/J.Compedu.2020.103850.
- [15] A. Santiago And L. Ray, "Navigating Support Models For Oer Publishing: Case Studies From The University Of Houston And The University Of Washington," Ref. Serv. Rev., Vol. 48, No. 3, Pp. 397-413, Jul. 2020, Doi: 10.1108/Rsr-03-2020-0019.
- [16] T. Luo, K. Hostetler, C. Freeman, And J. Stefaniak, "The Power Of Open: Benefits, Barriers, And Strategies For Integration Of Open Educational Resources," Open Learn., Vol. 35, No. 2, Pp. 140-158, May 2020, Doi: 10.1080/02680513.2019.1677222.
- [17] J. Littenberg-Tobias And J. Reich, "Evaluating Access, Quality, And Equity In Online Learning: A Case Study Of A Mooc-Based Blended Professional Degree Program," Internet High. Educ., Vol. 47, Oct. 2020, Doi: 10.1016/J.Iheduc.2020.100759.S

- [18] X. Zhang Et Al., "Accessibility Within Open Educational Resources And Practices For Disabled Learners: A Systematic Literature Review," *Smart Learning Environments*, Vol. 7, No. 1. Springer, Dec. 01, 2020, Doi: 10.1186/S40561-019-0113-2.
- [19] L. Todorinova And Z. T. Wilkinson, "Incentivizing Faculty For Open Educational Resources (Oer) Adoption And Open Textbook Authoring," *J. Acad. Librariansh.*, Vol. 46, No. 6, Nov. 2020, Doi: 10.1016/J.Acalib.2020.102220.
- [20] J. Schellinger And J. G. Coghill, "Open Education Resources: Are We Ready For Prime Time?," *J. Electron. Resour. Med. Libr.*, Vol. 17, No. 1–2, Pp. 49–55, Apr. 2020, Doi: 10.1080/15424065.2020.1760163.
- [21] M. F. Maina, G. Santos-Hermosa, F. Mancini, And L. Guàrdia Ortiz, "Open Educational Practices (Oep) In The Design Of Digital Competence Assessment," *Distance Educ.*, Vol. 41, No. 2, Pp. 261–278, Apr. 2020, Doi: 10.1080/01587919.2020.1757407.
- [22] K. Lee, "Who Opens Online Distance Education, To Whom, And For What?," *Distance Educ.*, Vol. 41, No. 2, Pp. 186–200, Apr. 2020, Doi: 10.1080/01587919.2020.1757404.
- [23] P. Kumar And N. Kumar, "A Study Of Learner's Satisfaction From Moocs Through A Mediation Model," In *Procedia Computer Science*, 2020, Vol. 173, Pp. 354–363, Doi: 10.1016/J.Procs.2020.06.041.
- [24] A. Gupta And P. Pathania, "To Study The Impact Of Google Classroom As A Platform Of Learning And Collaboration At The Teacher Education Level," *Educ. Inf. Technol.*, 2020, Doi: 10.1007/S10639-020-10294-1.
- [25] R. Pitt, K. Jordan, B. De Los Arcos, R. Farrow, And M. Weller, "Supporting Open Educational Practices Through Open Textbooks," *Distance Educ.*, Vol. 41, No. 2, Pp. 303–318, Apr. 2020, Doi: 10.1080/01587919.2020.1757411.
- [26] K. W. George And A. M. Casey, "Collaboration Between Library, Faculty, And Instructional Design To Increase All Open Educational Resources For Curriculum Development And Delivery," *Ref. Libr.*, Vol. 61, No. 2, Pp. 97–112, Apr. 2020, Doi: 10.1080/02763877.2020.1749753.
- [27] Y. Wang, C. Dong, And X. Zhang, "Improving Mooc Learning Performance In China: An Analysis Of Factors From The Tam And Tpb," *Comput. Appl. Eng. Educ.*, Nov. 2020, Doi: 10.1002/Cae.22310.
- [28] Kumar, K. S. (2018, April). Educational Philosophy Of Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331916406_Educational_Philosophy_Of_Dr_Babasaheb_Ambedkar
- [29] Kumar, K. S. (2018, October 3). Defiance Of Women With Disability. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328171795_Defiance_Of_Women_With_Disability.
- [30] Kumar, K. S. (2019, February). Electronic Content And Online Courses On Massive Open Online Course (Mooc) In India. Researchgate.
- [31] https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331097648_Electronic_Content_And_Online_Courses_On_Massive_Open_Online_Course_Mooc_In_India.
- [32] Kumar, K. S. (2018, November). Massive Open Online Courses: Pupils Involvement And Participation. Researchgate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/329167606_Massive_Open_Online_Courses_Pupils_Involvement_And_Participation.
- [33] Kumar, K. S. (2018, September). Digital Learning Tools For Education In 21st Century. Researchgate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327971917_Digital_Learning_Tools_For_Education_In_21st_Century.
- [34] Kumar, K. S. (2018, September). Social Media As A Learning Tool In Modern Education Trend. Researchgate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327971761_Social_Media_As_A_Learning_Tool_In_Modern_Education_Trend.
- [35] Kumar, K. S. (2018, April). Dr. Br. Ambedkar: Chief Architect Of Making Modern India. Researchgate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331916559_Drbrambedkarchief_Architect_Of_Making_Modern_India_One_Day_National_Conference.
- [36] Mani, M., & Prabu, M. M. Teachers Self-Efficacy Scale: Development And Validation, *Review Of Research*, 8(6), 1-8 (2019).
- [37] Mani, Mahendraprabu, Enhancing Self-Efficacy Of Higher Secondary School Students By Yoga Based Intervention, *Roots International Journal Of Multidisciplinary Researches*, 4(12), 10-13 (2017).
- [38] M. Mahendra Prabu, Life Skill And Soft Skill Through Teacher Education Program, *Research Directions*, 3(11), 1-6 (2016).
- [39] M. Mahendra Prabu, Inclusive Education, *An International Refereed, Peer Reviewed And Indexed Quarterly Journal In Arts, Commerce, Education & Social Sciences*, 5(2), 28-30 (2016).
- [40] G. Sivakumar, M. Mahendraprabu, A Study Of Self Concept And Adjustment Problems Of Prospective Teachers, *Review Of Research*, 6(3), 1-6 (2016).
- [41] G. Arumugam, M. Mahendraprabu, A Study On The Mental Health Of Higher Secondary Students, *Journal Of Contemporary Educational Research And Innovations*, 4(6), 43-46 (2016).
- [42] M. Mahendra Prabu, A Study On Knowledge Of Communicable Diseases And Its Relation With Environmental Awareness Ability, *Golden Research Thoughts*, 6(1), 1-4(2016).

- [43] G. Arumugam, M. Mahendraprabu, A Correlational Study Of Environmental Awareness Ability And Knowledge Of Communicable Diseases Among Higher Secondary Students, Indian Journal Of Applied Research, 5(1), 124-128 (2015).
- [44] M. Mahendraprabu, G. Arumugam, A Study Of Environmental Awareness Ability Of Higher Secondary Students, International Journal Of Modern Research And Reviews, 2(11), 508-510 (2014).
- [45] M. Mahendraprabu, G. Arumugam, Knowledge Of Higher Secondary Students About Communicable Diseases And Their Mental Health, Conflux Journal Of Education, 2(3), 76-79 (2014).
- [46] Mani, Mahendraprabu, A Study On Self Efficacy Of Higher Secondary Students With Respect To Locality Of The Schools, Think India Journal, 22(10), 807-813 (2019).